

The Application of Modern Control Theory To Improve The Quality of Motion Fidelity in Ground Based Motion Simulators

D. W. Repperger
 Building 33
 Armstrong Laboratory AL/CFBS
 Wright Patterson Air Force Base
 Dayton, Ohio 45433-6573

Abstract

Optimization methods utilizing LQ (linear quadratic) techniques are applied to develop improved motion fidelity of a 3 axes motion simulator. The motion simulator (centrifuge) is modeled as a 3 axes revolute robot. The optimization procedure is applied to minimize induced accelerations (Coriolis) that commonly occur. Computer simulations of these algorithms demonstrate that over 65 % reduction of the untoward accelerations can be obtained.

I. Introduction

One application of modern control theory is to enhance the fidelity of the performance of motion simulators by the minimization of unusual or untoward motions produced. Most ground based motion simulators all suffer to some degree from some lack of motion fidelity due to the fact that they are not truly aircraft in the specific flight scenario of interest. If, in the design of a simulator, it is possible to quantify any motion artifact as an isolated variable, then optimization methods could be used to minimize this artifact and evaluate any tradeoffs associated with this type of minimization.

The procedure utilized here is to model the motion simulator (centrifuge in figure (1)) as a large robotic system. One can view the motion of a robotic system in terms of the response of a coordinate frame moving through space and attached to the end-effector when it is in a position control mode and not in contact with the environment (Koivo [1]). At the end-effector, a key measure of performance or capability of the overall robotic system would be a definition of a set of all possible rotations and accelerations that could be produced for the device of interest. Any figure which

represents the capability region of the robot (e.g. an acceleration radius (Graettinger and Krogh [2]), an ellipsoid in Cartesian velocity space based on singular values (Yoshikawa [3], Maciejewski [4]), or other methods) is a function which changes along the path trajectory due to the dynamics of the actuators and the geometry of the robotic system. Coriolis, which occurs as a consequence of a coordinate frame moving relative to another moving coordinate frame, is a key problem when multi axes are utilized. In motion simulators, when viewing them within the context of a robotic system, the goal is to make the final accelerations and rotations appearing at the end-effector similar to a desired reference trajectory.

This paper considers the reduction of Coriolis accelerations which commonly occur when complex rotations or multi axes are utilized in the simulation of supermaneuverable flight trajectories performed by agile aircraft [5-7]. Two minimum Coriolis inverse kinematics algorithms are considered. The first algorithm contains zero Coriolis the second algorithm minimizes the Coriolis. The purpose of the development of these algorithms is to apply them to a motion simulator like a centrifuge to make the resulting motion fields more realistic to humans.

II. The Impact of Coriolis Accelerations on Human Subjects

Figure (2) illustrates the classical definition of Coriolis acceleration as originally defined by the French engineer, G. Coriolis. The vector ω has a direction out of the paper and the slider with linear velocity V moves relative to the rotating arm. The untoward action of the Coriolis acceleration which acts on the slider as indicated in the figure is satisfied by the relationship:

$$a_{Coriolis} = 2\omega \times V \quad (1)$$

which is in a direction orthogonal to both the arm and the ω vector. If a human subject were positioned on the slider on the rotating arm, and were to make any body motion in the direction of the slider movement (V), an acceleration $a_{Coriolis}$ would act on the subject in the direction of $a_{Coriolis}$ in figure (2). This is very counter intuitive to a human subject to experience an acceleration (or resulting force on his body) acting in this direction orthogonal to the moving slider.

III. Formulation of The Problem of Interest

Let $\Omega(t)$ represent the motion field desired at the end point of the simulator of interest from figure (1) and $\theta(t)$ the vector of joint rotations. The details of the choice of coordinate systems using standard Denavit-Hartenburg formulation and the derivation of the equations of motion can be found in [5-7].

It is noted that both $\Omega(t)$ and $\theta(t)$ can be broken up into two terms:

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega(t) &= \Omega_{nc}(t) + \Omega_c(t) \\ \theta(t) &= \theta_{nc}(t) + \theta_c(t) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where the subscripts nc and c refer to noncoriolis and Coriolis terms, respectively. Two optimization problems can now be formulated:

IV. Problem 1: Zero Coriolis in Attitude Space:

In this case it is desired to solve the following optimization problem by minimizing J_1 with respect to a scalar control variable $p(t)$ where:

$$J_1 = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{t_f} \{ \|\theta(\tau) - \theta_k(\tau)\|_{R1}^2 + (1 - p(\tau))^2 r2 \} d\tau \quad (4)$$

Here the state vector is θ_k and the control variable is $p(t)$. The time interval $t \in [0, t_f]$ describes the time duration in which the solution is desired. $\theta(\cdot)$ is a vector of joint angles that are desired since $\Omega(t)$ is known a priori. θ_k represents the actual joint angle time histories resulting from joint motions with reduced Coriolis. $p(t)$ will be defined as a result of the linear quadratic optimization procedure. $R1$ is a positive definite symmetric matrix, $r2 > 0$, and the norm denotes Euclidean norm. Minimizing J_1 is subject to the dynamic constraint (state vector equation for θ_k in terms of the control variable $p(t)$):

$$\dot{\theta}_k = p(t) [J2]^{-1} \Omega \quad (5)$$

where $p(t) \neq 1$ is selected to integrate the joint angles forward. The optimization of (4) subject to (5) also has a state variable path constraint during $t \in [0, t_f]$ of the form:

$$\Omega_c(t) = \Omega_c[\theta_k(t)] = 0 \quad (6)$$

It is noted that the hard constraint on the attitude variable in equation (6) is what gives problem 1 the classification as zero Coriolis in attitude space. A second solution to this problem is as follows.

V. Problem 2: Minimum Coriolis in Attitude Space

A second method involves some nonzero Coriolis, but reduced from the normal inverse kinematics expression for $\theta(t)$. In this case the objective is to minimize J_3 with respect to a scalar variable $p(t)$ where:

$$J_3 = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{t_f} \{ \|\Omega_c[\theta_k(\tau)]\|_{R1}^2 + (1 - p(\tau))^2 r2 \} d\tau \quad (7)$$

and with the dynamic relationship:

$$\dot{\theta}_k = p(t) [J2]^{-1} \Omega(t) \quad (8)$$

Again, as in problem 1, the state vector becomes θ_k and the control variable is $p(t)$. Note that Ω_c can be determined by the terms involving the cross products of joint velocities. Thus in problem 1 there exists a hard constraint on the Coriolis terms. In problem 2, however, the optimization procedure is used to minimize these terms but some artifact is permitted (resulting in the existence of nonzero Coriolis) through the tradeoff between the attitude variables and the joint commands. The appendix describes in detail the actual optimization procedure for the solution to problems 1 and 2. The method described by problem 2 is implemented in this paper.

VI. Results of The Optimization Procedure:

With reference to the appendix, using the assumption that $J2(\theta)$ was non singular and could be used as a simplification for the determination of the $p(t)$ equation (if not, $J2^{-1}(\theta_k)$ would be a more accurate approximation or other methods could be employed), it was also noted that in both solutions, the expression for $p(t)$ was found to be of the form:

$$p(t) = 1 + (\text{Coriolis reduction term}) \quad (9)$$

because if $p = 1$, then full Coriolis exists. The second term in equation (9) must reduce the Coriolis. This second term was found to be (in the solution of both optimization problems):

$$\text{Coriolis reduction term} = -(\tau_2)^{-1} \lambda^T (J_2)^{-1} \Omega \quad (10)$$

thus by judiciously selecting τ_2 , one can adjust the Coriolis effects to be made arbitrarily small.

To illustrate the applicability of this approach, this method will be investigated via a computer study of the mathematical model describing the motion simulator (centrifuge).

VII. Applicability of The Approach To A Motion Simulator:

To apply this approach to a motion simulator, it is first required to have available the Jacobian for the centrifuge simulator. In [5,6], it was determined that for a specific seat configuration:

$$J_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1, & 0, & s_2 \\ 0, & s_1, & c_1 c_2 \\ 0, & -c_1 & s_1 c_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

To illustrate the applicability of this approach, it will be demonstrated on a special motion trajectory termed the "Cobra". The Cobra is a supermaneuver which has been demonstrated at airshows [9,10] and has special significance in a combat scenario whereas it appears that when an aircraft performs this supermaneuver, it rapidly slows down in the sky as a tactical maneuver to confuse an opposing aircraft.

For the objective function J_3 in equation (7), the choice is made of $R_1 = 2I$, $\tau_2 = 8, 1$, and 0.2 . This results in the following two point boundary value problem:

$$\lambda(t_f) = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$\dot{\lambda}^T = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_k} [\Omega_c^T R_1 \Omega_c] \quad (13)$$

$$p(t) = 1 - (\tau_2)^{-1} \lambda^T (J_2)^{-1} \Omega \quad (14)$$

$$\dot{\theta}_k = p (J_2)^{-1} \Omega(t) \quad (15)$$

It is noted that the term $\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_k} [\Omega_c^T R_1 \Omega_c]$ is obtained in closed form with the main concern to minimize accelerations in the lateral Gy direction for each of the

λ components. The Gy component is the most disturbing to humans and it is desired to change the influencing functions λ as per this Gy component. The equations for the λ variables now become (with the assumption that R_1 is diagonal with diagonal elements r_1):

$$\dot{\lambda}_1 = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_{1k}} r_1 [\bar{B}^2] \quad (16)$$

$$\dot{\lambda}_2 = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_{2k}} r_1 [\bar{B}^2] \quad (17)$$

$$\dot{\lambda}_3 = 0 \quad (18)$$

$$\lambda(t_f) = 0 \quad (19)$$

The differential equation for λ_3 has zero on the right hand side due to the independence of the terms of Ω_c on θ_3 . Since the vector $\lambda(t_f) = 0$, this leaves λ_1 and λ_2 as the only nonzero variables. The relationship for Ω_c is substituted and the partial differentiation is first taken and then the adjoint equations are then integrated backwards. Since:

$$\dot{\theta}_k = p(t) [J_2]^{-1} \Omega \quad (20)$$

and:

$$p(t) = 1 - (\tau_2)^{-1} \lambda^T (J_2)^{-1} \Omega \quad (21)$$

This corrects the θ_i terms. The θ_i are then integrated one step forward to obtain their respective corrections. The Coriolis can then be recalculated with these changes in the joint commands.

From figure (3) it is seen that a substantial reduction of Coriolis is possible. Comparing over time the sum of the squares of the \bar{B}_3 terms, the minimum Coriolis is calculated for $\tau_2 = 1.0$ and compared to the original Coriolis (resulting in a 65.4 % reduction in Coriolis accelerations in the Gy direction produced by the motion simulator when it uses this new inverse kinematics algorithm).

VIII. Summary and Conclusions

An optimization procedure is utilized to minimize the Coriolis accelerations that occur from a centrifuge simulator as it emulates a specified motion field. Two solutions to this problem are considered. It is demonstrated that a reduction of over 65 % of the Coriolis can be accomplished through the weightings selected for the objective function.

Appendix:

Problem 1 falls within the context of a linear quadratic optimization problem with path constraints along the optimal trajectory [8]. Problem 2 is also a quadratic optimization problems, with the control entering in a linear manner. We now reformulate each optimization problem, defining the state variables, the control, and the procedure to solve each problem.

Problem 1: Minimize with respect to the control variable $p(t)$:

$$J_1 = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{t_f} \|\theta(\tau) - \theta_k(\tau)\|_{R1}^2 + (1 - p(\tau))^2 r_2 d\tau \quad (22)$$

where the state variable dynamic constraint is specified by:

$$\dot{\theta}_k = p(t) [J2]^{-1} \Omega \quad (23)$$

and state variable path constraint is given by:

$$\text{Let: } C = \Omega_c(t) = \Omega_c[\theta_k(t)] = 0 \quad (24)$$

The solution of this problem is specified once the Hamiltonian $H(\cdot)$ is chosen. For this case:

$$H = \frac{1}{2}(\theta - \theta_k)^T R1 (\theta - \theta_k) + \frac{1}{2} (1-p)^2 r_2 + \lambda^T [p (J2^{-1})] \Omega + \mu C \quad (25)$$

where the λ vector is the adjoint state variable and μ is another influence function. It is noted that in equation (23) the control p is linear in the state equation, and that $\Omega(t)$ and $\theta(t)$ are known and specified a priori. The necessary conditions for optimality require:

$$\dot{\lambda}^T = -H_{\theta_k} \quad (26)$$

with transversality condition:

$$\lambda(t_f) = 0 \quad (27)$$

Thus:

$$\dot{\lambda}^T = -(\theta - \theta_k)^T R1 - \mu \frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta_k} \quad (28)$$

The second necessary condition is:

$$\pi_p = 0 \quad (29)$$

which yields:

$$(p-1) r_2 + \lambda^T (J2)^{-1} \Omega = 0 \quad (30)$$

which results in:

$$p(t) = 1 - (r_2)^{-1} \lambda^T (J2)^{-1} \Omega \quad (31)$$

Thus a two point boundary value problem is established in which the adjoint equations for $\lambda(t)$ are integrated backwards using equations (27) and (28) and $p(t)$ is calculated forward from equation (31). Interestingly enough: $p = 1 +$ (a second term). If $p = 1$, then Coriolis is present. The second term must be the Coriolis reduction term which adds linearly. The details of the solution of problem 2 are now presented.

Problem 2: Minimize with respect to the control variable $p(t)$:

$$J_3 = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{t_f} \|\Omega_c[\theta_k(\tau)]\|_{R1}^2 + (1 - p(\tau))^2 r_2 d\tau \quad (32)$$

subject to a dynamic constraint on the state variables of the form:

$$\dot{\theta}_k = p(t) [J2]^{-1} \Omega(t) \quad (33)$$

For this case a Hamiltonian is defined as follows:

$$H = \frac{1}{2} \Omega_c^T R1 \Omega_c + \frac{1}{2} (1-p)^2 r_2 + \lambda^T [p (J2)^{-1} \Omega] \quad (34)$$

The necessary conditions for optimality require:

$$\dot{\lambda}^T = -H_{\theta_k} \quad (35)$$

with transversality condition:

$$\lambda(t_f) = 0 \quad (36)$$

Thus:

$$\dot{\lambda}^T = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_k} [\Omega_c^T R1 \Omega_c] \quad (37)$$

The second necessary condition ($H_p = 0$) yields:

$$(p-1) r_2 + \lambda^T (J2)^{-1} \Omega = 0 \quad (38)$$

hence the familiar control law results (identical to equation (31)):

$$p(t) = 1 - (r_2)^{-1} \lambda^T (J2)^{-1} \Omega \quad (39)$$

since $\Omega_c(\theta_k)$ is known, this problem is easily solved. Finally it is noted that we have assumed $(J2[\theta])^{-1} \approx (J2[\theta_k])^{-1}$ to eliminate the complexity of this factor into the analysis. If the $\frac{\partial (J2)^{-1}}{\partial \theta_k}$ term were to appear in any of the λ equations, the problem becomes increasingly more difficult.

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FIGURE (1) THE DES (DYNAMIC ENVIRONMENT SIMULATOR)

Fig (2) - The Classical Definition of Coriolis Acceleration

B3 Bar Coriolis For The Cobra Maneuver The Effect of r2 on the Solution

